

Readiness and Barriers to Good Retirement towards Retirees' Socio-Economic and Physical-Mental Health Program in Private HEIs in Northern Luzon

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ABSTRACT

Retirement is an individual's exit from the workforce which is accompanied by decreased psychological commitment to and behavioral withdrawal from work. It may further refer to early or compulsory retirement where an individual has to leave from his work. It is understood also as a decision making process which emphasizes that retirees make a motivated choice to decrease their psychological commitment to work and focus on other life activities like family and community related activities. At the same time it is also taken as an adjustment process where emphasis is given not to the decision itself but on the nature of retirement like timing of the retirement, previous preparation for the retirement, the resources available in retirement and the activity change resulting from retirement among others. Thus preparation for retirement is very important. This study aimed to determine the level of readiness of retirees for retirement; identify considerable barriers to a good retirement and determine as well as propose certain programs, projects and activities that would promote a good retirement for retirees. It was found out that retirees are well prepared about their retirement. They claim that they are well prepared personally and by their employers. However, in spite of such preparations, it was found out that there are still considered socio-economic and physical mental health concerns that bar them from enjoying a good retirement. The results of the study showed that socio-economic concerns are intertwined with the physical-mental health concerns in that latter is usually dependent on the former. Socio-economic preparation determines physical-mental health concerns in retirement. Furthermore, it is then recommended that employers and other organizations should work together for the crafting and implementing a socio-economic and physical-mental health program for the welfare of retirees in their pre-retirement and retirement stages respectively.

Keywords:

Retirement Planning, Retirement Decision-making, Retirement Transition and Adjustments, Bridge Employment, Retirement Barriers

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I. INTRODUCTION

According to Borji (2016) there are three countries which total population is more than 20% of the total population with the age of 65 or older in 2015. The countries are Germany, Italy and Japan. But he writes that by 2020, 13 countries will have a similar figure and by 2030, 34 countries will follow. Around the globe, there is a decrease in working-age population, increase in health problems and health care costs, increase in dependency ratio, and changes in the economy. This is true to most industrialized countries. However, it cannot be denied that year in and year out, there are Filipinos growing older and for many working Filipinos, this is felt only after retirement. The Philippines having a young and booming population might be the reason why few studies were conducted related to gerontology or studies relating to aging and issues in after retirement.

But many recognized that the decrease in the age of exit from gainful work has been one of the most profound structural changes in the past 25 years. Health promotions at retirement is of considerable importance for retirees and aging people as well as our political, social and health care leaders responsible for drafting policies and programs to help improve health and wellness in older adults. In the Philippines, there are several laws that cater to the needs of our retirees or our aging population like the senior Citizen's law. But how far does this law help in the holistic wellness of the growing aging population? With the young population that we have, those who retired or had reached the age of retirement might not be able to work anymore with the booming young population. But this would also mean the exit in the workplace of those who have already mastered their craft or their profession.

Such exit from gainful work would have an implication to the economy and of course to their health condition and lifestyle. In other countries they have homes for the aged where they are cared for medically. But this is not the case in the Philippines. Filipinos have strong family ties, so older people in the family are usually staying or cared for at home. But with an exit from a gainful work, it is expected

that retirees will have a different lifestyle or life activities which may have a consequence to their socio-economic, physical, psychological and even mental health. Moreover, in today's changing times, do Filipinos, characterized as having strong family ties, care for the aged?

It cannot be denied that our retirees and the aging population had been the socio-economic cornerstone of our family and society. At the same time, they are also the embodiment of our culture and values. That is why for Filipinos we have much respect for our elders. But what is happening now to them? Do we have baseline information regarding their socio-economic and their health condition? Aside from receiving pensions, discounts from basic goods and services and to our senior citizens even cash dole out from the government, what could be done for them especially in the regional or local level?

Literatures and experience show that there are many challenges and opportunities among retirees and the aging population in general. For some retirees, their retirement means new routine, new life activities which may affect their health and even their social life. There are those who would say that they feel anxious, depressed, they could hardly get out of bed in the morning and they miss their co-workers. Others would like to return to work for they have not yet thought of retiring for good but since they have reached the compulsory retirement age, they cannot do anything but to retire. They think of having time with their families but they end up living alone since their children and grandchildren are staying away from home. Lucky are those, while being retired, are still able to find a gainful work but many would only now depend upon their pensions or their family for support. There are also those who cannot enjoy retirement due to financial constraints. They have not planned well their finances while being able to work. And with such financial constraints, health care services for them would be in peril. They would now be only dependent upon the basic services from the government which may not always be enough to respond to their health needs.

In the case of Nueva Vizcaya, there seem to be no organization yet that caters to the needs of retirees except the mandated Senior Citizens group, alumni associations and other NGOs. In most of these organizations they only cater to the financial or economic needs of our retirees and they only come in the life of retirees after retirement. However, among retired educators and educational institutions' personnel they can still be a strong and good source of manpower for socio-economic and physical-mental health activities that would benefit not only themselves or their families but even the society as a whole.

Damayon, et al (2019) found out that "barriers to socio-economic promotions are anxiety on family's hospital or medical needs, no time for social activities due to family, no savings upon retirement, and unable to join any organization after retirement while barriers to physical-mental health promotions are no regular medical check-up, have hypertension, no life or health insurance, and no regular exercise." These were some of the barriers among the retirees of a higher educational institution. However, with the limited number and the homogeneity among the respondents, there is a need to establish a baseline barriers to retirement where programs/projects could be establish for the promotion of a better life at retirement.

This study would venture more on describing the phenomena surrounding the lives of retirees of private higher educational institutions in Nueva Vizcaya to come up with baseline information about retirees and at the same time craft programs/projects as bases for future activities for this special group of retirees. This study specifically aim to establish baseline data on a) level of readiness of retirees for retirement; b) Possible barriers to good retirement and c) identify and develop programs/projects to prepare retirees for retirement along pre-retirement, retirement and adjustment and adaptation in retirement.

II. METHODOLOGY:

This research employed a quantitative and qualitative method of gathering data. Furthermore, arm-chair and visual anthropology were also used in sourcing out the topic being studied from libraries, the internet and other literature sources. A questionnaire was also floated to ascertain the level of readiness of respondent –retirees for retirement. The respondents were retirees and candidates for retirement from the four private higher educational institutions in Nueva Vizcaya. In the analysis and interpretation of data on level of readiness of retirees for retirement, the "temporal process model of retirement" a psychological model for understanding retirement was utilized. This model was explained by Schultz & Wang (2011) and Wang & Schultz (2010) that there are three sequential stages of retirement that allows researchers to study more closely ageing processes particularly retirement.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Level of Readiness of Retirees for Retirement

Retirement has many stages and in these different stages requires different kinds of preparations or activities. The three stages of the temporal process model of retirement are the retirement planning, retirement decision, and retirement transition and adjustment. Retirement planning is the phase where an employee starts his preretirement preparation wherein an employee starts to discuss plans with friends, family and colleagues. This phase is classified into financial and cognitive planning (Taylor-Carter, et al, 1997). This is shown to be crucial for structure, social interaction and maintaining a standard of living into retirement (Hershey, et al, 2013).

Table 1: Level of Readiness in Pre-Retirement Preparation (Retirement Planning Phase)

Level of Preparation	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)
Low Extent	8	18.2
High Extent	31	70.5
Very High Extent	5	11.4
Mean = 3.0318, Standard Deviation = .50659, Overall Level (Qualitative Description): High Extent		

Scale: Very High Extent (3.5-4.0), High Extent (2.5-3.49), Low Extent (1.5-2.49), Very Low Extent (1.0-1.49)

The table above shows that there are 18.2 % who have low extent pre-retirement preparation, 70.5% which comprises the majority have a high extent of pre-retirement preparation while 11.4% have a very high extent of pre-retirement preparation. The above percentages are complemented by the Mean of 3.0318 with a qualitative description of high extent. Furthermore, the standard deviation shows that the level of readiness in pre-retirement preparation is spread out among the respondents. But it could be perceived that there is a high extent of pre-retirement preparation among the respondents.

The above data only shows that retirees are well prepared for their retirement. This is supported by a high percentage of agreement that they have plans to do in their retirement and also a high percentage on their admission of excitement and looking forward to their retirement. This data only imply that retirees and even employees are really looking forward to retirement and many of them are already preparing themselves very well. But in spite of high extent of pre-retirement preparation, we cannot also deny the fact there are those with low extent of pre-retirement preparation. This could be interpreted either way, these employees, on the one hand, are not yet preparing for retirement since they are so much immersed or committed in their work that retirement has not come to their mind. On the other hand, there are employees who are not yet thinking of retirement since retirement means it is the end of their occupation, the source of their livelihood.

According to Schultz & Wang (2011), retirement planning is the phase where an employee starts his pre-retirement preparation by discussing plans with friends, family and colleagues. So while there is hype for some when retirement is being discussed among friends, family and colleagues, there is also anxiety on the part of those who had not really prepared for the time that one has to stop from a gainful occupation. This is really a challenge among private educational institutions where retirement benefits may not be that advantageous to retiring employees unlike in the public sector whose retirement benefits are mandated by law.

Pre-retirement preparation always involves financial and mental preparations. This phase is classified into financial and cognitive planning (Taylor-Carter, et al, 1997). This is shown to be crucial for structure, social interaction and maintaining a standard of living into retirement (Hershey, et al, 2013). It seems that they are pointing to the reality that pre-retirement preparation always involves financial and mental preparations and that each preparation affects each other. Those who prepared less financially might frown about the idea of retirement the same is true with those who had not prepared themselves mentally. Kim and Moen (2001) found that unfavorable attitudes toward retirement were related with the absence of retirement planning and the failure to seek information about retirement. And Damayon, et al (2019) found out that good retirement requires pre-retirement preparation. This was observed in the case of many retirees going into bridge employment after being retired by their employer. Thus, self – preparation coupled with employer’s preparation of its employees for retirement are factors for good retirement.

The next stage is the retirement decision phase wherein one has to weigh the values of work and leisure over time against individual circumstances to make a retirement decision. Others retire as a result

of a rational deliberation by comparing the financial resources accumulated and financial resources needed in retirement (Laitner & Sonnega, 2013). Since not all retirement are voluntary, there are those who decide to retire due to their attitudes towards their jobs, employers, careers, and even workplace norms (Zhan, et al, 2013) and others due to health status, worker's productivity, job characteristics and others (Schultz & Wang, 2007). In the Philippines, there are mandated retirement ages depending on the profession both in public and private employment. Awareness of this mandated retirement age requires that one has to prepare oneself for this stage.

Table 2: Level of Self-Preparation for Retirement

Level of Preparation	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)
Very Low Extent	1	2.3
Low Extent	10	22.7
High Extent	23	52.3
Very High Extent	10	22.7
Mean = 2.9416, Standard Deviation = .64650, Overall Level (Qualitative Description) : High Extent		

Scale: Very High Extent (3.5-4.0), High Extent (2.5-3.49), Low Extent (1.5-2.49), Very Low Extent (1.0-1.49)

The table above shows that there were 22.7% and 52.3% high extent and very high extent self-preparation for retirement. The result is supported by its Mean of 2.9416 with a qualitative description of high extent. But it is important to mention that there are 22.7% with low extent 2.3% with a very low extent self-preparation. The analysis of the data implies that while there are retirees or employees who really are concern about their self-preparation for retirement there are those who has not given it a thought. The data also imply that that self-preparation may be dependent upon the decision to retire. Those who have decided to retire on a certain age or are aware of the mandatory retirement age are those who had an extensive self-preparation financially and mentally.

In certain contexts, a conducive work or job environment makes workers closer to one another and strengthens the bond of friendship. But retirement breaks the bonds at least geographically. And so workers may opt to plan to delay retirement or to just wait for the mandatory retirement age and then go for retirement. According to Jaworski, Reed and Vernon (2016) work-related attitudes such as high job satisfaction may predict delayed retirement. But in general according to them, the impact of job satisfaction or good working environment on retirement decisions may depend on other factors like diverging impact on workers of high job satisfaction with sufficient versus insufficient savings. Thus we go back again to financial planning as the paramount starting point of all retirement consideration.

In any preparation for retirement, understanding what retirement is all about is of primal importance. Understanding its intricacy may help someone to prepare to this stage. One must understand that retirement is an individual's exit from the workforce which accompanies decreased psychological commitment to and behavioral withdrawal from work (Wang & Shi, 2014). In this study it may further refer to early or compulsory retirement where and individual has to leave from his work. It is also understood as a decision making process which emphasizes that retirees had to make a motivated choice to decrease their psychological commitment to work and focus on other life activities like family and community related activities (Wang & Schultz 2010). At the same time it is also taken as an adjustment process where emphasis is given not to the decision itself but on the nature of retirement like timing of the retirement, previous preparation for the retirement, the resources available in retirement and the activity change resulting from retirement among others (Szinovacz 2003). In the table above, it can be shown that retirees have a high level of self-preparation for retirement. But another question would be how do employers prepare their employees for retirement? This would be the next logical question in knowing the level of readiness for retirement of their respective employees.

Table 3: Level of Employer's Preparation for its Employees Retirement

Level of Preparation	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)
Low Extent	16	36.4
High Extent	23	52.3
Very High Extent	5	11.4
Mean = 2.6727, Standard Deviation = .65711, Overall Level (Qualitative Description) : High Extent		

Scale: *Very High Extent (3.5-4.0), High Extent (2.5-3.49), Low Extent (1.5-2.49), Very Low Extent (1.0-1.49)*

The table above shows that there are 11.4% of the respondents who claim that they were prepared by their employer to a very high extent, 52.3% or majority of the respondents were claimed to be prepared by their employer to a high extent and a 36.4% of the respondents claimed that they were prepared by their employers to a low extent. In spite of the presence of a low extent employers' preparation for retirement, the table still shows a good picture on employer's preparation of their respective retirees for retirement with a Mean of 2.6727 which has a qualitative description of high extent. An observable spread out responses is shown by its standard deviation of .65711 which implies that respondents have diverse perception on the matter.

This scenario maybe understood that, while in general the employers have a high extent preparation of the respondents for retirement, there are those who perceive that they are not prepared well. It must be pointed out that preparation may also affect a decision for or against retirement. The data showed that to a high extent, the retirees were socio-economically as well as physically and mentally prepared by their employers for retirement.

It must be emphasized that mental or psychological preparations not to mention financial preparation are very important according to several studies for they have an impact to retirement itself. These studies showed that pre-retirement jobs, job and career attitudes, organizational policies and even workplace norms have implications to the retirement process. Gobeski and Beehr (2008) found that workers in stressful jobs were more likely to take bridge employment in a different field than take career bridge employment or full retirement. Wang, et al. (2008) and Kim and Feldman (2000) found that retirees who had higher job satisfaction or longer job tenure at preretirement jobs were more likely to engage in career bridge employment than in bridge retirement in a different field or in full retirement.

The decision phase of retirement is basically the weighing in of the values of work and leisure over time against individual circumstances. Feldman and Beehr (2011) has characterized this phase into three cognitive stages where an employee as to imagine the possibilities that one has to brainstorm possible futures, assess when it is time to let go of the job, that is, consider the past experience at work, and put concrete plans into action at present, that is, use the compiled information to take steps toward retirement in the present. In this study, the respondents have a high extent perception on their employers' preparation for them for retirement. It may then also mean that retirees are able to make good decisions whether to consider retirement or not. All of these matters, self and employer's preparation are important to one's adjustment or adaptation to retirement itself.

Table 4: Retirement Adjustment and Adaptation

Level of Preparation	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)
Very Low Extent	1	2.3
Low Extent	8	18.2
High Extent	25	56.8
Very High Extent	10	22.7
Mean = 2.9129, Standard Deviation = .65443, Overall Level (Qualitative Description) : High Extent		

Scale: *Very High Extent (3.5-4.0), High Extent (2.5-3.49), Low Extent (1.5-2.49), Very Low Extent (1.0-1.49)*

In the table above, one could see that majority of the respondent-retirees could well adjust and adapt themselves to the new environment of retirement. 22.7% say that they could adjust and adapt to a very high extent while 56.8% say that they could adjust and adapt to a high extent. Meanwhile 18.2% and 2.3 % say that they could adjust and adapt to retirement to a low and very low extent respectively. The data then manifest that while there are retirees who were well prepared to adjust and adapt to the new environment of retirement life, there are those who could hardly cope up with the new challenges or requirements of retirement. But the Mean of 2.9129 also sets the picture that overall, the adjustment and adaptation preparation is to a high extent.

Good adjustment and adaptation to retirement maybe attributed to the preparations made not only of the retiree but also by the employer. The third and last phase is the transition and adjustment phase wherein the main focus is the changes in the daily activities which may include leisure, volunteer work, or even bridge employment (paid work). Leisure activities are described by enjoyment, aesthetic appreciation, intimacy with friends and family, involvement in organizations religious activities, physical

exercise and work or doing a hobby (Nimrod et al. 2009). Volunteer work may involve caring for one's family member or volunteering outside homes with civic organizations (Kaskie et al. 2008). Involving transition and adjustments, life course theory in retirement argues that the person's individual history (e.g. work and leisure habits) and attributes (e.g. health and financial status) influence the transition and adjustments (Donaldson et al. 2010).

In this study, respondents claim that they do not have problems adjusting to their new routine. Several of them are engaged in organizational activities or even into part time jobs to keep themselves busy and fit. In the study of Damayon, et al (2019), it was found out that the perceived most important consideration for any preparation for retirement is financial and followed by health considerations. It was further observed that the physical-mental health concerns are intertwined with the financial or socio-economic status of retirees. Thus, financial preparation and cognitive or mental preparations for retirement is of paramount importance.

2. Barriers to Good Retirement

Retirement is an individual's exit from the workforce which accompanies decreased psychological commitment to and behavioral withdrawal from work (Wang & Shi, 2014). Most if not all would like to have a good and happy retirement. But having one depends mainly on good planning and preparations. However, planning and preparations themselves may not guarantee a good and happy retirement. "There is often a combination of excitement and anxiety as people approach retirement. The excitement comes from having more free time, but the anxiety comes from figuring out how much can I afford to spend? And what will I do with all that time?" (The Retirement Problem, 2014). But again, this is when one has something to spend. This could be true when one has really financially planned one's retirement. But retirement is not all about money for people in retirement has also to plan to be more productive and stay engaged.

The decision to retire or retirement itself has a life-altering implications for finances, health and psychological well-being in later life. There could be factors that may hinder or serve as a barrier in the optimum exercise of the possibilities that retirement may provide. And since retirement implies nonparticipation from the work force, exit from one's employer, reduce earnings, receipt of pension income, it means that there will be more time for self, family and the society (Shultz & Wang, 2011).

As retirement age arrives, the effects to the social, financial, physical and psychological or mental well-being comes into the picture. Wang et al (2011) claims that financial well-being can be defined as "the extent to which the person feels satisfied with one's financial status and is able to maintain effective financial functioning." Thus, engagement in preretirement preparations is very important since the physical-mental well-being is "the extent to which there is absence of physical diseases and functional limitations (Zhan et al, 2009)." One may think of aging well and have a graceful life in retirement but getting there is usually a challenge. This is so because it can be painful to leave one's work especially when one has closely identified oneself to his job. There could be many consequences like loss of friends, importance and even vitality. Most often, one's identity and social value is associated with work such that retirement would mean losing both. But the biggest challenge may creep in when there is a gap between expectations and reality. It is here that retirees need a sensible self-reflection about themselves or people around them have to do something to help them. With this in mind, the respondent-retirees have identified several barriers for socio-economic and physical-mental health promotions.

Table 5: Socio-Economic and Physical-Mental Health Barriers to Good Retirement

Socio-Economic Barriers to Good Retirement			Physical-Mental Health Barriers to Good Retirement		
Barrier	f	%	Barrier	f	%
Retirement pay was made to only partially pay financial obligations	28	63.8	No regular medical check-up (Medical check-up is sought only when needed)	31	70.5
No life or health insurance policy	28	63.8	Feeling obligated to work for the family's basic needs	28	63.8
Finding a new work after retirement to financially support myself and my family	23	52.3	Anxiety about family's hospital or medical bills	26	59.1
Monthly pension is not enough to	20	45.5	Worries for family's financial	24	54.5

cover my family's basic financial needs			support		
No savings upon Retirement	19	43.2	Could hardly afford myself or my family's hospital or medical bills (feeling of helplessness)	24	54.5
Cannot afford a life or health insurance policy	14	31.8	I feel bad since I cannot provide my family's needs after Retirement	18	40.9

The table above shows the perceived barriers to a good retirement. The left column contains the perceived socio-economic barriers to good retirement while the left column contains the physical-mental health barriers of good retirement. In terms of the socio-economic barriers, the highest percentage goes to the concern on partial payment of financial obligations and no life or health insurance policy with 63.8%. This is followed by finding a new work after retirement, monthly pension is not enough for the family, no savings after retirement and non-affordability of a life or health insurance policy. In terms of the physical-mental health barriers, no medical check-up tops all the other perceived barriers with 70.5% and followed by feeling obligated to work for the family's basic needs, anxiety about family's hospital or medical bills, worries for family's financial support, could hardly afford the family's hospital and medical bills and feeling bad since one cannot provide the family's needs after retirement.

The data manifests a concern on the economic self-preparation of the retiree and by his employer. Retirement is said to be a time when a gainfully employed individual will now enjoy the fruits of his labor. But retiree-respondents now expressed recognition that there is a concern on the economic preparation of the retirees and even by their employer. A closer look on the data shows that the perceived socio-economic barriers are closely connected with the physical-mental health barriers to good retirement. Any problem in the socio-economic dimension of retirement affects the physical-mental health aspect of retirees. It causes anxiety, worries and other mental disturbances on the part of the retirees.

The study of Jaworski, Reed and Vernon (2016) confirms the result of the study where they found out that insufficient savings, the need to pay for medical care of a family member or lack of health insurance are barriers for one to decide on retiring and all the more in the enjoyment of retirement. Hence, in many research studies about retirement, financial literacy gets the most attention. And that it is often emphasized that engagement into preretirement financial planning has been repeatedly documented to lead better financial well-being in retirement which may have important implications to physical-mental health well-being (Wang and Shi, 2014).

The finding that retirement pay is not enough to pay financial obligations and that one needs to find another work for the family's needs confirmed the study of Marshall et al (2001) which showed that "the number of dependents and costs related to dependent care often jeopardize people's financial well-being in retirement." It explained that the more dependents the retiree has and the more costs incurred due to dependents, the more likely financial well-being in retirement will suffer which may in turn have considerable implications to the physical-mental well-being of a retiree. It seems to imply that family planning also has an impact to retirement itself.

Furthermore, the above results confirm the study of Stanton (2006) and Singh (2006) which expressed that health insurance in retirement is also related to physical-mental well-being. They claimed that retirees enjoy better physical-mental well-being when their health insurance offers more extensive coverage and they incur lower personal financial costs. And that the better quality and more consistent health insurance are more likely to have a better physical-mental well-being in retirement. But which or who should provide all this services? The retirees could not do it alone without the help of other institutions, like the employer, insurance providers whether public or private and other organizations.

In the study of Damayon, et al. (2019), it was found out that in a higher educational institution in the Nueva Vizaya, Philippines, there are several barriers to retirement like the worries for medical needs and time for social activities, no savings, inability to join organizations, no regular medical check-up, increasing health issues like hypertension, no regular exercises and no life or medical insurance. These results show that there are problems in the processes of retirement and in the retired life itself.

It is noteworthy that in the stages or phases of retirement, pre-retirement, retirees and employers' preparations were rated to a high extent. But the data shows that if there is to be a preparation, the most basic preparation is financial or economic preparations. It is a reality that retirement benefits depend on

one's employment status. And it is known that private higher educational institutions in the region do not really provide a better retirement plan than those in the public sector. If indeed, good retirement is hampered by financial concerns which redounds to concerns in physical-mental health concerns then something has to be done. Programs, projects and activities including policy formulation must be formulated with financial planning and preparations at the center where others come into the picture.

Table 6: Activities that Retirees want to do during Retirement

Activities	Description	Mean	SD	QD
Spend time with Family	Use my free time to help my family or other families in need of a babysitting. This could even be a way to strengthen the bond with my family and others in the community.	3.45	.791	High Extent
Reengage with Spiritual Activities	Meditate, learn yoga, and get involved in our church activities	3.41	.583	High extent
Start a new Hobby	Now is the time to expand on my interests. Take on a new hobby such as fishing, hiking, gardening, painting, photography or even just playing cards.	3.41	.622	High Extent
Retirement preparations	I like that my employer/s should prepare me economically and mentally for my retirement	3.39	.538	High Extent
Travel	Now that I do not have vacation time limitations, I will travel around the country or the world.	3.23	.642	High Extent
Engage into farming	I like to venture into farming, gardening or simply landscaping my backyard. I will also take some time to take care of some live stocks or pets,	3.20	.823	High Extent
Retirement and other financial Contribution	I like to increase my retirement contribution or other contributions that would help me socio-economically in the future after a gainful work.	3.09	.676	High Extent
Start a Business	Now that my career is over, start that business I have always wanted. Consider using my career experience to start a consulting firm or take my existing part-time business and expand it into a full-time enterprise.	3.09	.802	High Extent
Get a Part-Time Job	Find a fun part-time job with a company I love. Having this job will not only bring in a little extra income, but it will give me a place to socialize each day.	2.98	.876	High Extent
Be a Mentor	Find a young person to mentor. Many young people would love the chance to learn from the experienced and successful. Take time out of my week to change the life of someone else.	2.95	.806	High Extent
Social Organization	Join meet-up groups that are geared to socialization, certain interests or even volunteer work. Organizations centered around books, chess, charity activities, or for their own welfare and mutual protection.	2.93	.900	High Extent
Investment Seminars and investment opportunities	I like to attend to investment seminars so I know how to manage my retirement pay as I retire and maybe looking for investment opportunities for me and my family.	2.91	.910	High Extent

Volunteer	Use my time in retirement to give back. Contact my school, local government/church or other charitable organization to find volunteer opportunities that suit my skills.	2.84	.776	High Extent
Teach	Use my hard-earned wisdom and experience to teach others. Start a free course at my local community. I could even possibly teach at a local community college or university.	2.84	1.098	High Extent
Join a Fitness Group	To stay committed to my new active lifestyle, join a team of others who are also looking for accountability toward their fitness goals. Work toward getting in the best shape of my life.	2.84	.805	High Extent
Downsizing debts	I wish to be advised on how I handle my credits so that they are paid off before I have retired	2.75	.918	High Extent
Insurance Policy	I wish to avail an insurance policy way before my retirement so that I would not have problems with my medical needs	2.73	.788	High Extent
Work as a consultant	I will use my skills and knowledge to help organizations or individuals as consultant. Consulting requires skills and knowledge but it may build more socialization and income generation opportunities.	2.66	.963	High Extent
Overall Mean		2.83	.413	High Extent

Scale: Very High Extent (3.5-4.0), High Extent (2.5-3.49), Low Extent (1.5-2.49), Very Low Extent (1.0-1.49)

The table above shows the different activities that retirees would like to engaged with. They are activities that have a Mean with a qualitative description of high extent and are arranged from the highest to the lowest Mean. From these different activities one could see that retirees would first and foremost want to spend their time with their family. They like to make up with the time which was mostly spent with work. Furthermore, one could notice that these activities could actually be categorized into several themes, they are:

- 1) Family Concerns;
- 2) Personal and Leisure Concerns;
- 3) Pre-Retirement Concerns;
- 4) Volunteerism;
- 5) Socio-Economic concerns; and
- 6) Physical-Mental Health Concerns.

1) Family Concerns. Spending time with family has the highest Mean of 3.45 with a high extent qualitative description. This result as mentioned above could be explained by the fact that retirees are already severed from their work and so they would like to make up with the time when they could not do perform their family duties like babysitting their grandchildren, sending them to school, visiting their children, keeping the family together. Moreover, one could see that almost all the other activities are mostly meant for the welfare of the family as a whole.

This is something given especially for Filipino workers who are described to be family oriented workers. In this study and speaking from experience, one can see and observed that even after retirement, parents are always concerned about the welfare of their children whether their children are gainfully working or not. This is a manifestation that even prior or after a gainful work, employee-retirees are really after their family's welfare. And all the more when they have all the time with them not anymore bounded by the work that they have before retirement. This result is supported by the ideas of Dorfman, Loraine (2020) that

One of the most satisfying and productive ways of investing one's time and energy in retirement can be found in family relationships. While relationships with friends, neighbors, and former coworkers are also important for retirees, family is the social

institution that is the basis of our social support and exerts a lifelong hold and influence on us. Imperfect though the family may be, it is where most people turn for comfort and sustenance. Family ties can provide a rich source of involvement for retirees and can be a valuable source of support for them in the years ahead.

- 2) **Personal and Leisure Concerns:** Retirees like to reengage themselves with spiritual activities and start a new hobby. These two has a Mean of 3.41 with a high extent qualitative description. Travelling around the country or the world came next with a Mean of 3.32 and a high extent qualitative description. And others would like to engage into farming (or gardening and landscaping) with a Mean of 3.20 and qualitative description of high extent. These activities could be explain by the reality that retirees, especially those who had committed themselves to their work, may not have much time to work on their personal interests and involve themselves to religious-spiritual activities and retirement is indeed an opportune time.

Prior to the issues of old age comes retirement, many who are in the active workforce usually make good plans for a better life upon retirement. No more deadlines, no more meetings, you own your own time now. One could travel, enjoy life with the family, do things that one has longed to do that cannot be done while working and many others. But what if one's life after retirement is not the one pictured? It would be a very devastating experience. A practice professor of management in the person of Stewart Friedman (The Retirement Problem, 2014) said that as one person grows older "the questions people ask at earlier stages of life become more profound at the later stages." There are questions about whether their lives' purposes were accomplished for the end of life becomes clearer for them. In the psychosocial theory of Erikson, this is called generativity (Erikson, cited in Rathus 2014). This might be able to explain the desire of retirees to re-engage into religious-spiritual activities to find meaning in their lives as one requirement for a good and happy retirement.

- 3) **Pre-Retirement Concerns:** One cannot give what one does not have. This statement describes what happens in retirement. Once retirement age is reached, there is no turning back. One has to live with what one has. Thus, for the retirees, retirement preparation is very important. In fact it has the third highest Mean of 3.39 with a high extent qualitative description. The retirees would like their employers to have prepared them economically and mentally. These desire for an economic and mental preparations come along the desire to increase financial contribution to the retirement fund (if there is any) (Mean=3.09), investment seminars and investment opportunities (2.91), downsizing debts (Mean=2.75) and Life and Health Insurance Policies (Mean=2.73). The data show that retirees are much concern about their economic as well as their health condition during their retirement and so pre-retirement preparations on these areas were considered by them as to priority.

Respondent-retirees earlier claimed that they are prepared well socio-economically and physical-mentally. But while they are well prepared for their retirement, experience might have shown them that planning is different from reality. Damayon et al (2019) have found that that retirees are cognitively aware that retirement stage would come whether they are in dire financial needs or is suffering from health issues it has come to the point that some of them have accepted that their retirement pay will be used to pay their financial obligations. This is why many of them are into bridge employment. Bridge employment, according to Wang et al. (2009), is the "pattern of labor force participation exhibited by older workers as they leave their career jobs and move toward complete labor force withdrawal." Furthermore, they claimed that bridge employment could take many forms like when the work hours are reduced compared to preretirement jobs, the bridge employment could serve as phased retirement which has been shown to help retirees ease into their retirement.

But nothing could beat someone who is really prepared for retirement. Experience wise, this might be a reason why they emphasized the value of pre-retirement preparation. If retirees were prepared before retirement, there will be no reason for them to go into bridge employment for themselves and for their families and would only have time for their families and for leisure. It might be there and then that they could have enjoyed a good retirement. In the study of Damayon *et al* (2019), they found out that retirees do not have problems or issues about their current socio-economic and physical-mental

condition, they seem to have accepted already their current situation, but could have wished for a better financial preparation in view of retirement.

- 4) **Volunteerism:** Our data show that retirees like also to volunteer in the school, church or even in the community (Mean=2.84), being a mentor to someone (Mean=2.95), to teach for free (Mean=2.84) and work as a consultant (Mean=2.66). Retirees after a gainful work like to engage themselves into volunteer work like mentoring young professionals, share their expertise, their hard earned wisdom by teaching or lecturing and even becoming a consultant to activities that may provide more socialization and economic opportunities. In fact, one respondent had expressed his desire of putting up a cooperative for retirees.

There are researches that indicated that it is by giving back and finding one's sense of purpose are keys to the happiness in retirement. "While giving back can mean boosting charitable institutions, for a growing number of retirees it often comes in the form of significant volunteer position...the most successful people in retirement look to use their talents and passions to make contributions. People who are at this stage are focused on their legacy. " One has to be actively engaged with oneself and ask what one really desires to leave behind (The Retirement Problem, 2014). It is in these instances that retired individuals need social support. And we can learn from Robertson (2017) that ageism is a serious matter. Since any perception that we have about ageing will have an impact, negative or affirmative, to our older population and even among the young generations.

- 5) **Socio-Economic Concerns:** This concern cuts across the other concerns. Notable of these concerns is the desire of retirees to start a business (Mean=3.09), get a part time job (Mean=2.98), joining social organizations (Mean=2.93) and other activities that cut across the other themes. It is noteworthy that after retirement, work does not stop for retirees. They still want to engage in a gainful work like starting a business where their knowledge about management and the like are put into actual practice with them as entrepreneurs. Others choose to engage into part time job, jobs that may really be in line with their interest inside or outside the educational system. Another very interesting interest of retirees is their enthusiasm to join social organizations where they could share their interests and even for volunteer work. Other concerns pertaining to the retirees socio-economic concerns and are found in other themes are engagement into farming (Mean=3.20), retirement fund contribution (Mean=3.09), Investment seminars and opportunities (Mean=2.91), downsizing debts (Mean=2.75), being a volunteer (Mean=2.84), teaching (Mean=2.84), mentoring (Mean=2.95), and being a consultant (Mean=2.66).

In the previous study conducted by Damayon, et al. (2019), they found out that retirees, who are expected to stop working and enjoy the leisure of retirement either individually or with the family members likes to enter into bridge employment. This was specific for teacher-retirees. One could sense here that those who had worked long enough in an institution have troubles leaving their work. However, Adams and Beehr (1998) and Adams, et al. (2002) have found that "one's organizational commitment and career attachment were negatively related to the decision to retire." While this may be true to several studies, the above study found otherwise. The above result of the current study is a manifestation that respondent-retirees are very much attached that while they have already retired there is the desire to be still part of the institution. But such desire must be correlated with their socio-economic-physical-mental health condition, that is, they feel that they have to work even after retirement for their family's economic and health welfare.

- 6) **Physical-Mental Health Concerns:** These concerns refer to the activities that are meant to counter retirees' physical-mental struggles or conditions that may affect his individual or mental life. It also cuts across other categories. From the table above, one of the several activities that respond to these concerns is joining a fitness group with a Mean of 2.84 and a qualitative description as high extent. It is notable that retirees, while in their advanced age, would still really desire to stay in shape. They must be aware that one of the best way for them to enjoy a good retirement is keeping themselves in good shape and health. They wanted to prepare for this life by a good insurance policy (Mean=2.73), they wanted to keep themselves busy and keeping their sanity by engaging into a new hobby

(Mean=3.41), involve themselves into religious-spiritual activities (Mean=3.41), and most especially to ensure their family's welfare (Mean=3.45).

It can be observed from the above table that almost all socio-economic activities are actually activities that would redound to the physical-mental health welfare of the retirees. This supports the finding of this study that physical-mental health welfare is intertwined with the socio-economic condition of retirees.

Retirement, where age is considered as advanced, leads one to the awareness that one has lived longer and that this is the stage that one has to enjoy life itself. But in a study by Graham (2018), he concluded that "living longer does not in itself make us better off. As our population continues to age, we will need to make important and potentially difficult choices about how we want to care for the elderly. Crucially, strategies to promote healthy ageing may not only ease the burdens on society, but help to ensure that our longer lives are better lives even in a philosophical sense." He is saying that life at retirement must be something that must not be taken for granted. Society must still be concern about them even if they are not anymore into a gainful work. We can see from the above data that retirement could not stop our elders to contributing something to our society.

The result of this study confirms the study conducted by Damayon, et al (2019) that many of the retirees have accepted the fact that health issues come with aging. The health concerns are already given facts for people who are ageing. Thus, they only have to find ways to stay in shape. And one way of staying in shape is going into bridge employment. This will not only keep them in shape but also provide something for their families as it was found out that the respondent-retirees' physical-mental health concerns are intertwined with their financial or socio-economic status. Many of them are anxious and worrisome about the economic and health status of themselves and their family. Thus, financial preparation and cognitive or mental preparations for retirement is of paramount importance.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

From the data above analyzed and interpreted, it can be concluded that

1. Retirees from private higher educational institutions in Nueva Vizcaya have a high level of preparedness or readiness for their retirement which means that they had prepared themselves and by their employers socio-economically and physical-mentally well for their retirement;
2. In spite of the high level of preparedness or readiness of retirees for retirement, the retirees from private higher educational institutions in Nueva Vizcaya still has perceived socio-economic and physical-mental health concern that bars them from an experience of a good retirement; and
3. Programs, Projects or Activities rest mainly on pre-retirement concerns and retirement concerns which can be organized, maintained and monitored by employers and other social organizations. These PPA's must respond to the perceived barriers to a good retirement and commit to the possible activities that retirees desire to participate with before and during retirement.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS: PROGRAMS, PROJECTS and ACTIVITIES

As a result of the study the following PPAs in their general form are recommended:

Programs	Pre-Retirement			Retirement			
	Projects	Activities	Persons/Organizations Involved	Projects	Activities	Persons/Organizations Involved	
Socio-Economic Welfare Program	Financial Literacy	Investment seminars and opportunities	Employer-employee and other organizations	Volunteerism	Mentoring	Retirees, Retirees' Organization and other NGOS / GOs	
		Entrepreneurial trainings			Teaching		
	Financial Capacitation	Conferences about Insurance Policies	Employer-employee and other organization		Consultation		Involvement in school, church and community
							Organizing an

		Downsizing debts	s	Personal and Leisure Projects	activity for (group) Hobby	Retirees, Retirees' Organization and other NGOS / GOs
		Increase Contribution to the Retirement Fund			Tips for farming/Gardeni ng	
Physical -mental Health Welfare Program	Physical and mental Fitness	Family Day, Sports and other activities	Employer-employee and other organization s	Formation of Retirees Association or organization	Sharing of Hobbies	Retirees, Retirees' Organization and other NGOS / GOs
	Annual Medical Check up	Physical and medical check up			Fitness activities	
					Socialization activities	
					Volunteer Activities	

The researchers are cognizant that that they could not implement the PPAs by themselves. The programs could be embedded in the higher educational system whereby in collaboration with employees who are soon to retire could work together for the establishment of a good socio-economic and physical-mental health projects where the different activities could be carried out for the benefit and welfare of the employees or soon to be retirees. This is also true to Retirees Organizations, NGOs and GOs who can work closely with retirees taking advantage of their knowledge, talents and skills in the development of activities that would make the life of the retirees a good and a happy one.

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